

THE APPLICATION OF GAMES IN TEACHING VOCABULARY AT PRIMARY SCHOOL.

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ABSTRACT

Over the last decades, the level of people's interest in the English language has increased markedly. Nowadays the English language in Uzbekistan is taught in all public schools, directly from the 1st grade. However, it should be noticed that children at an early age are prone to rapid fatigue and loss of concentration. In particular, learning vocabulary is considered as an important complex process, as a result of which it is expected to enrich the vocabulary and expand the horizons of learners. Researchers often argue about which method of teaching vocabulary is the most effective for children. However, it is undeniable that there is a difficulty in concentration during the lesson for a long time. Dewaele & Thirtle (2009) claim that foreign language learning, at the same time, can be succeeded as long as it is fun, exciting, and achievable. As a result, a diverse number of techniques for learning L2 have emerged.

Background

Over the last decades, the level of people's interest in the English language has increased markedly. Nowadays the English language in Uzbekistan is taught in all public schools, directly from the 1st grade. However, it should be noticed that children at an early age are prone to rapid fatigue and loss of concentration. In particular, learning vocabulary is considered as an important complex process, as a result of which it is expected to enrich the vocabulary and expand the horizons of learners. Researchers often argue about which method of teaching vocabulary is the most effective for children. However, it is undeniable that there is a difficulty in concentration during the lesson for a long time. Dewaele & Thirtle (2009) claim that foreign language learning, at the same time, can be succeeded as long as it is fun, exciting, and achievable. As a result, a diverse number of techniques for learning L2 have emerged.

Gaming activity is considered as one of the most indispensable tools in teaching foreign language to primary school learners. There are lots of advantages for both the children and the teacher. S.A. Bakhsh (2016) who conducted such an approach, focused on the process of active application of games. However, the author faced with several challenges such as the noise and unorganized classroom, the lack of time dedicated to games and the usage of mother tongue during the lesson. Despite this fact, S.A. Bakhsh (2016) confirmed that using

games will enable young learners to acquire the lesson with fun where they can remember all the vocabulary easily.

W. M. Yipa and C. M. Kwan (2006) offer the application of online games in vocabulary learning. Their research proves that learners playing online vocabulary games tend to learn better and could retain the learnt vocabulary for a longer period and retrieve more words than those who simply attended face-to-face lessons without accessing the vocabulary games. Although

Kiili (2005, p. 14) expressed serious doubt about the effectiveness of drill and practice games to learning, our research indicates that vocabulary learning can

be significantly improved by their use. Despite all benefits, it should be mentioned that there may occur difficulties with the use of IT technologies in the classroom for young learners.

E. Sulistianingsih, R.Febriani(2019) suggest using Application Board Games. During conducting these games, students learn more to complete some cases of the latest vocabulary to make them a winner. So, they are going to learn English vocabulary without feeling depressed and dull. (Endang Sulistianingsih, Rizka Febriani, JCS. Pradjarto, 2019) The study was conducted carefully enough and impressive results were demonstrated. Except this, there were given the number of suggestions and recommendations for subsequent studies.

Thus, this study aims to reveal the effectiveness of using games in explaining vocabulary, adapted from the framework developed by Sahar Ameer Bakhsh (2016), which can be used to teach the English language at primary schools. To that end, this investigation is guided by the following research question:

Do vocabulary games affect L2 learners' vocabulary acquisition?

Methods

Participants

The role of participants was great in conducting a research. They worked as they used to; it was not obligatory for them to know that they were being tested in a certain research. The participants of our research aiming at finding out the role of games in L2 vocabulary acquisition were the third-grade pupils of public school. They were of the same age, but their level of language proficiency differed because in the same class study active and passive pupils. Active pupils perceive information without difficulty, while passive ones have some drawbacks in perceiving. The pupils of high activeness were good at speaking, writing, reading and listening. They were well acquainted with the materials of their level and age. However, the second group of pupils who acquired low activeness faced with complexity in these skills. It occurred due to the fact that they came to the class without preparation. The research was conducted in two groups. There were 15 participants in each group. The participants of the our research were 9 year old. The amount of active and passive pupils in two groups correlated to each other. There were male and female pupils in the researched groups. The number of girls and boys in the groups was balanced. The two groups had almost the same features. The single difference was their L1. The first group was Russian and the second group was Uzbek.

Research Design

There were two variables that we were going to use in the research. Vocabulary games was the independent variable, the impact of which we were able to observe in the final analysis. L2 learners' vocabulary acquisition was the dependent variable, that was beyond the control of the researcher and was considered to be an indicator of the effectiveness of the entire study. It should be noticed that vocabulary games was a categorical variable and L2 learners' acquisition – continuous variable. This data was operationalized through conducting a questionnaire.

To find out the effect of games on learners' vocabulary achievement, we decided to apply quasi-experimental research. This kind of research was considered to be the most appropriate as we relied on convenience sampling due to infeasibility. To get the data, we used two groups of learners in the research. They were the experimental group and the comparison group. The experimental group was given a new topic through applying various kinds of vocabulary games. On the other hand, the comparison group was taught the same topic but in traditional way of teaching.

Scoring Procedures

The tests done by the participants of our research were assessed according to fifteen-point scale. Three of us were involved in assessing learners' acquisition as raters. One of us had tight relationship with learners, thus she assessed relying on intra-rater (but for herself to check whether the games were efficient for vocabulary acquisition and for pupils who were interested in knowing their mark). However, for collecting reliable data we relied on instrument reliability. The minimum score was 0 and the maximum 15. The minimum score in the post-test in the treatment group was 9 points out of 15 while in the comparison group it was 6. The maximum score in the treatment group was 14 out of 15 whereas the comparison group achieves 10 points. The minimum score for the pre-test in the treatment and comparison groups was 0 out of 15 and the maximum score in the both of the groups is 2 points.

One point was assigned to each item in the pre- and post- tests. In the pre and post-tests there were given 15 items. If each of them was assigned as 1 point, it totally gave 15 points.

Reliability

We calculated through internal consistency.

Our data was calculated through Cronbach's alpha and langtest.jp. First, we coded our data in Excel (like 1=correct, 0=incorrect). Afterwards, we went to langtest.jp, clicked on Cronbach's Coefficient Alpha, copied and pasted our data from Excel.

According to Cronbach's coefficient alpha we got raw alpha 0.799 and std.alpha 0.998 in the post-test of the treatment group and raw alpha 0.785 and std.alpha 0.995 in the post-test of the comparison group. The given statistics witnesses the reliability of our post- test.

Results and Discussion

First, we investigated whether there was any difference in English proficiency between the treatment and comparison groups before and after the treatment. Table 1 shows that there was no difference in the mean scores between the comparison and treatment groups in the pre-test, whereas the treatment group has a much larger mean score than that of the comparison group in the post-test. Treatment group showed a mean score of 11.8 whereas comparison group had a mean score of 8.2.

As shown in Figure 1, the mean score from the post-test ($M=11.8$) was much higher than that in the pre-test ($M=0.8$). The paired samples t-test (see Table 1) shows a statistically significant difference between the two tests ($t=-25.5$, $p<.001$) The statistical evidence clearly indicates that the treatment group outperformed the comparison group in the post-test.

Figure 1. Difference between the pre- and post-test.

Table 1 Paired samples t-test Results

Test type	Group type	N	M	SD	t	p	d
Pre-test	Comparison	14	0.786	0.802			
Pre-test	Treatment	14	0.786	0.802			
Post-test	Comparison	14	8.214	1.188	-29.645	< .001	-7.923
Post-test	Treatment	14	11.786	1.718	-25.450	< .001	-6.802

As shown in Figure 2, the treatment group outperformed the comparison group in regard to English achievement at school. Treatment group showed a mean score of 11.8 whereas comparison group had a mean score of 8.2. The independent samples t-test (see Table 2) revealed that there is a statistically significant difference between the two groups with a large effect size ($t= -6.398$, $p<.001$, $d= -2.418$).

Figure 2. Difference between Comparison and Treatment groups. Table 2

Independent Samples t-test Results

	N	M	SD	t	p	d
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Comparison	14	8.214	1.188	-6.398	<.001	-2.418
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Treatment	14	11.786	1.718
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The results appear to suggest that learning foreign language through applying games is more effective than activity-based learning. As it was predicted, games have a great influence on L2 vocabulary acquisition. During our research we have observed two groups (the treatment and comparison groups). The post- test of the treatment group gave successful results in comparison to the comparison group. According to the mean of the post-test taken from the two groups, the application of games has significance in vocabulary acquisition. Although Sahar Bakhsh (2016, p. 123) claimed that there is a probability to be faced with practical challenges of implementing games in teaching process, our research indicates that vocabulary learning can be significantly improved by their use. This research can be useful for teachers who are interested in teaching vocabulary. They should have to consider whether they will use vocabulary games as a warm-up activity at the beginning learning stages or a regular long-term learning tool.

Conclusion and Limitations

Our research witnesses the effectiveness of games during language learning process among primary school pupils. In our research the effectiveness of games is considered from the perspective of vocabulary. Before conducting the research as researchers we familiarized a number of articles relying on the application of vocabulary within language learning classes. Thus, we made our mind up conducting research in this area. In contrast to other researchers, who carried out the research on the effectiveness of games within language learning classes,

in our research we have accentuated on the influence of games on a certain group of learners in learning a certain aspect of the target language. In other words, only primary school pupils' vocabulary acquisition was tested before and after game applied lessons. As it was mentioned there were two participant groups in our research: the treatment group and the comparison group.

Two similar groups gave the same results in the pre-test, but totally different results in the post-test. Judging by the post-test taken from the treatment and the comparison group we as researchers can come to the inference that games really positively affect vocabulary acquisition among primary school pupils. The research witnessed that the treatment group gave better results than the comparison group. Thus, language teachers are suggested to apply games in teaching vocabulary at primary school, which ease memorizing and motivate at the same time. However, some limitations were admitted during our research. These limitations were connected with the span between the lessons and pre and post-tests. Due to the quarantine the school where the research was carried out was closed for one week and consequently there was enough span between the first lesson and the second lesson in the treatment group and the comparative group. The Other limitations were not noticed. In our research we tried to follow the lesson plan, take into account pupils' age, level and language proficiency. Our research instruments were reliable and we were able to gather reliable data which was very important. Our research has proved our preview. After fulfilling the research we witnesses that the application of games really increase vocabulary acquisition. As researchers we recommend the language learning teachers to apply games during the lessons in learning vocabulary at primary school.

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